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DigiAge

LIFE AFTER COVID-19 – HOW OLDER ADULTS ARE ADAPTING TO RAPID DIGITALISATION WORLDWIDE

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1. INTRODUCTION

The outbreak of COVID-19 in 2020 catalysed a rapid acceleration in digitalisation globally. Digitalisation, defined as the integration of digital technologies into everyday life, became central to how societies functioned during prolonged lockdowns. While countries adopted broadly similar digital strategies to manage pandemic-related disruptions, national responses also reflected local infrastructural, cultural, and social differences. Pre-existing levels of digital advancement and population-specific digital adaptability further shaped these varied outcomes.

In the field of healthcare, England's digital transformation, for example, was particularly pronounced. While the first point of contact for most patients with the National Health Service (NHS) would have typically involved face-to-face or telephone interaction prior to the pandemic, post-pandemic, digital platforms such as the NHS website or the NHS app are more likely to serve as the initial interface. Between October 2021 and September 2022, the NHS website alone was visited by 1.2 billion people, most of whom were seeking Covid-related information. By 2024, the sites' weekly average visitor number had reached 23 million, making it one of Europe's foremost online health information sources. The NHS App, on the other hand, had over 28 million registered users by 2023. It has become the primary portal for accessing personal health records, scheduling appointments, and managing prescriptions (NHS, 2023). It is not surprising that it is often described as the "front door" to the NHS.

Still focusing on the health sector, the increase in the use of smartphones and mobile health apps during COVID-19 was prolific in most countries, enabling users to keep track of their health on the go, communicate with healthcare providers, and check their health records. Wearable devices like

fitness trackers and smartwatches also flooded the market, promoting preventative health care behaviours and monitoring vital signs. Ongoing innovations in big data, machine learning, AI, and genomics are today expected to revolutionise healthcare still further by transforming diagnostics, personalising medicine, and speeding up drug discovery. Robotic surgery and care are no longer figments of the imagination, and virtual reality and augmented reality technologies are already being used in medical training, surgery, and mental health therapy.

However, the technological revolution spurred by COVID-19 extended far beyond healthcare and many of the changes the pandemic gave rise to look as though they are here to stay. Financial services, retail, employment, education, and social interactions all migrated further online, with consequences for society and the environment that still remain ill-understood. Emerging research provides some pointers as to the pros and cons of these developments, and in this report, we look at how the digitalisation spurred by the pandemic has impacted older adults in different countries.

This report was produced under the **DigiAge Project (2022-2025)**, England, undertaken by Lancaster University in collaboration with University College London (UCL). This project focused on how digitalisation impacts older adults, critically examining factors that contribute to an unequal distribution of benefits afforded to older adults by the digital economy in the areas of finance, communication, and health.

Although studies show that older adults became more adept at using digital technologies to stay in touch with family and friends during the pandemic in some countries (for an example from Canada see Sixsmith et al.

2022)¹, research in the UK has found that in 2021, two in five people aged 75 or older (40%) and more than one in eight of those aged 65 to 74 (12%) made no use of the internet (Age UK, 2021). By 2023, many here continued to find it harder than their younger counterparts to adjust to rapid digitalisation, struggling with issues like a lack of confidence and broadband access (Clayton et al., 2023). Furthermore, the United Kingdom (UK) cost-of-living crisis has made participating in the digital economy even more challenging, with many people, especially older ones, running the risk of digital exclusion from essential services and opportunities (Lloyds Bank UK, 2023; Soubutts et al., 2025). Taking a global perspective can help situate such findings and get a better picture of how older adults have been and continue to be impacted by rapid digitalisation.

The findings presented in this report are drawn from a purposive literature review and semi-structured interviews conducted with 40 older adults in the northwest of England as part of the DigiAge project. They provide insight into how older adults relate to digital technology, what they value about it, and what concerns them. We also discuss some country-specific measures taken to support older adults with the digital transformation (summarised in Appendix 1, p. 49), and identify topics for further research (Appendix 2, p. 50).

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Literature Review

¹ Sixsmith et al. (2022) found that during 2019, 11.3% of 65-74 year-olds and 11.1% of 75+ year-olds used their landlines to make phone calls, while in 2020, 16.2% of 65-74 year-olds and 22.3% of 75+ year-olds used computer video calls or smartphones to do so.

To examine how the COVID-19 pandemic affected older adults' relationships with digital technology and how they were impacted by rapid digitalisation across different global contexts, a purposive literature review was conducted. The review included searches across major academic databases, including ACM Digital Library, PubMed, ProQuest, Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar. These were focused on titles and abstracts using combinations of relevant keywords, grouped into three main categories:

1. *COVID-19-related terms*: "COVID19", "COVID-19", "Coronavirus", "Pandemic"
2. *Age-related terms*: "Aging", "Senior", "Aged", "Elderly", "Old"
3. *Digital-related terms*: "Digital", "Digital Technology", "Telecare", "Telehealth", "Digital Divide", "Digital Exclusion", "M-Health",

Reference lists of selected articles were also reviewed manually to identify additional relevant studies. The sources were managed in an MS Excel spreadsheet. The search strategy was adapted for each bibliographic database, and the search was conducted between February and August 2024. In addition to peer-reviewed academic literature, the review included grey literature sourced from university research centres, civil society organisations, international bodies, and private sector reports. The review also integrated findings from the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA) - a key partner in the DigiAge project. ELSA provides 20 years of longitudinal data on older adults in the UK, offering insights into the intersections of ageing, technology use, and social inequality. For this report, only ELSA data relevant to digital inclusion and exclusion were considered.

The rationale for our geographical scope was to concentrate on a selected group of countries where studies on the digital impacts of the pandemic had already been conducted. Selection was based on the availability of research that considered socio-cultural and economic differences in shaping older adults' relationships with digital technology. Additionally, we were interested in country-specific strategies aimed at supporting older adults in navigating the digital transition, some of which are summarised in Appendix I.

The reviewed studies primarily focused on countries within the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), as well as the European Union (EU), the United States, Canada, Australia, Saudi Arabia, and Singapore. The purposive nature of this literature review - rather than a fully systematic approach - was intentional. The goal was to develop a broad understanding of how older adults' digital engagement evolved during the pandemic, to highlight cross-national differences, and to identify areas requiring further research (see Appendix II).

2.2. Interviews

During 2023-24, two rounds of semi-structured interviews with 40 older adults from the north-west of England were conducted with the aim of exploring their experiences with digital technology and digitalisation. The interview guides included questions on their usage of technology pre-, during and post-pandemic, to learn more about any barriers or challenges participants may have faced and any changes in their technology use.

Following written informed consent from participants, interviews were audio-recorded, and the data analysed using Braun & Clark’s reflexive thematic analysis (2006) to help draw out themes. Underpinned by a pragmatist epistemological position that recognises the potential benefits of technology while also acknowledging the heterogeneity of older adults and their right to not engage, informal member checking (Roller and Lavrakas, 2015) was employed throughout data collection and analysis phases to help mitigate against researcher bias.

Brief **demographic details** on the participants are given in **Table 1** below.

Round 1 (March – June 2023)	
Age	68-92
Gender	12 female, 4 male
Ethnicity	White
Location	All residing in a small city in NW England
Previous occupations	Childminder, teacher, homemaker, supermarket checkout assistant, payroll clerk, nurse, social worker, university professor, administrative roles and telecoms engineer
Technical ability	Mixed, ranging from having no mobile phone to using smartphones, PCs, tablets and smartwatches daily
Round 2 (February – June 2024)	
Age	65-88
Gender	17 female, 7 male
Ethnicity	White
Location	All residing in a small city in NW England
Previous occupations	Nurse, army officer, administrative roles, call centre staff, university lecturer, accountant, homemaker, weaver, social worker, insurance officer, ticket officer, researcher
Technical ability	Mixed, ranging from having no mobile phone to using smartphones, PCs, tablets and smart watches daily

Table 1: Demographics of Interview Participants (Rounds 1 and 2)

3. FINDINGS

3.1. Digital Technology Usage

A study carried out by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in 2020 found that internet use in **OECD countries** early on during the pandemic changed little, with demographic differences remaining pronounced: 'Although 58% of those aged 50-74 used the Internet daily in 2019 – up from only 30% in 2010 –,’ it noted, 'this remains well below the average share of daily Internet users aged 16-24 (the so-called “digital natives”), which was close to 95%.' (OECD, 2020: p2). By 2022, these figures were very different for the older user group. Now, across the OECD, an average of around 98% of 16-24 year-olds used the internet (a slight increase) with 81% of 55-74 year olds using it (a large increase) (OECD, 2024). That there are significant geographical variations in these figures was also highlighted by the OECD. For example, internet use in 2022 among 16-24 ranged from 100% in Austria, Iceland, Luxembourg, Norway, Portugal and the United Kingdom, to 86% in the United States, and among 55-74 year-olds, from 99% in Norway to 53% in Turkey (ibid).

One country in the **EU** where internet usage among older adults is high is **Sweden**, one of the most digitally advanced nations in the EU after Denmark and Finland. Here, 88% of the population were e-government users in 2022 (introduced in 2001), and over 70% of Swedes aged between 66 and 75 and more than 50% over the age of 76 used the internet daily (Mylonopoulou et al., 2022). According to the EU’s Eurostat interactive tool on “Digitalisation in Europe – 2024 Edition” (hereafter Eurostat, 2024) 66.4% of Sweden’s population have basic or above basic digital skills, and 78% used smart home entertainment in 2022. Mylonopoulou et al. (2022)

explored how the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) changed among older Swedes due to COVID-19 restrictions. 74 women and 45 men completed their questionnaire, of whom 41% were aged between 65 and 75, 50% between 76 and 86, and 9% between 87 and 90. Most of these respondents were highly educated and 82.2% used computers daily for work. Compared to 2017, Mylonopoulou et al. found that for 48% of respondents, technology use during the pandemic had stayed the same, while for 52%, it had increased. Of these 52%, many used the internet more for online shopping (41%), watching TV (46%), reading newspapers (31%), and obtaining health information (33%). 23% also sent more emails, and 33% used it more for video calls. For 14.3%, ICT had gained more significance for socializing, and 17.9% had begun using it for learning, sustaining a hobby or activity, or looking for extended family (17.9%). The Swedish National Bank, meanwhile, reported that more citizens over the age of 65 made use of online payment facilities. This shows how the pandemic led to an increase in internet use among older adults in Sweden.

Factors here that were identified as enabling this increase were infrastructure improvements (e.g. fibre technology) and the provision of support services by the Swedish government and the private sector to support older adults with digitalisation. One nationwide strategy adopted aimed at adults over the age of 65 was a TV program called "Seniorsurfarna" (Senior Surfers), launched during the pandemic to help older adults gain digital skills. Mylonopoulou et al. conclude that these factors combined - improved infrastructure, digital skills training, increased and easily accessible online services, and affordable mobile technology - were instrumental in enabling older adults cope with digitalisation in Sweden during the pandemic.

In contrast, in **Portugal**, Eurostat figures for 2023 showed that just over half the population (56%) possessed basic or above basic digital skills (Eurostat, 2024). While Richardson et al (2020) have commented on the rapid expansion in the use of digital tools in many European countries following the onset of the pandemic, in Portugal, “remote consultations, and different e-Health solutions available to the population proved to be below expectations.” (Diehl et al., 2022: 2). According to a systematic literature review conducted by Abbaspur-Behbahani in 2022, the provision of m-Health services to the older population during the COVID-19 pandemic made great strides in many countries, helping to keep older adults and healthcare professionals safe and providing essential support such as therapy, information, self-help, monitoring, and mental health support. In Portugal, however, the digital infrastructure for providing healthcare solutions lagged behind, with challenges remaining regarding “privacy and security, interoperability, and inclusion” (Portela et al., 2021).

To grasp other factors influencing digital technology uptake following the outbreak of the pandemic in Portugal, a small qualitative study was conducted by Diehl et al. in 2020/2021 as part of the EU SHAPES project (2020-2023; Smart and Healthy Ageing through People Engaging in Supportive Systems). This study involved ten older adults aged between 70 and 77 years old, selected from a broad sociocultural and demographic spectrum to ensure it included people from varied life situations, with different levels of digital skills, and different health conditions. Eight participants had access to high-quality internet at home, while two had no internet access. Most participants reported a medium to high degree of digital technology usage (influenced by gender, age, and education levels), and being comfortable with digital technology

For most, however, technology usage during the COVID-19 pandemic changed rapidly, transforming many of the activities previously undertaken in person (face-to-face). Digital technology was used more to keep in touch with family and friends, combating loneliness, undertaking exercise routines at home, keeping informed (especially about COVID-19), and managing financial matters and other daily tasks. To cope with these changes, most participants relied on family members for technical help, for example, regarding how to use video conferencing. For the two participants in the study who reported their digital technology usage as 'low', it mainly played a role in keeping in touch with family and friends through instant messaging or for video calling. One of these participants lived in a rural area and was not keen on acquiring digital technology or learning how to use it. She mistrusted digital technology, especially smartphones.

This study concluded that although Portugal is a country with a large proportion of older adults (23.4% are 65+ years old, according to the provisional 2021 census), many of them face barriers and limitations to using digital technology. According to Diehl et al. (2022: 9), most Portuguese older adults do 'not have high levels of digital technology usage, internet access, and new technologies,, rely heavily on instant messaging and video calling applications,' and lack knowledge about other 'potentially relevant technologies. Internet access also remains a challenge.

The **US-focused** National Health and Ageing Trends Study (NHATS), a nationally representative panel study started in 2011, conducts an annual survey of Medicare beneficiaries aged 65 and older that emphasises oversampling underrepresented subgroups. During the COVID-19 pandemic, from June to October 2020, it carried out a COVID-19 supplemental mail-survey, collecting responses from 3,188 participants on their technology use

before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. This allowed for retrospective comparisons of change. Analysing the results of this survey, Drazich et al. (2023) found that due to lockdown restrictions, older adults performed more technology-based activity, more technology-based healthcare communication, and more technology-based food acquisition. A significant increase was also noted in the use of video chat for social communication. 740 participants (25.5%) mentioned that they had become acquainted with a new technology during the pandemic. Increase in technology use was greater in adults below the age of 80 compared to those over 80 year of age.

Another **US** study conducted by Ray et.al. (2022) looked at how older adults coped with the introduction of online conferencing tools during the pandemic. They interviewed 25 older adults aged between 60 and 89 years old who lived in independent/assisted communities and found that they all used a wide range of online tools, especially Zoom, taken up by 24 participants after the onset of the pandemic. Other tools used included WebEx, Skype, FaceTime, Google Meet and Microsoft Teams. The study showed that younger participants (aged between 60 and 67) tended to switch between the tools they used, relying on FaceTime and WhatsApp when talking with family, and Zoom and WebEx when participating in formal, structured group activities like online classes, group activities and professional meetings. To overcome technical problems, some participants formed communities of practice, something we also encountered in our empirical work, discussed below. Participants who were still employed at the time of Ray et al. conducted their study confirmed that they intended to keep using videoconferencing and collaborative tools for work-related activities post-pandemic. Reasons mentioned for this were time-savings (e.g. not having to commute to work/meetings), environmental benefits

(e.g. reduced air pollution due to less traffic), and the decreased risk of catching/passing on COVID-19.

Another study conducted in the **US** by Richards et al. (2021) investigated how social media platforms, phones and other forms of digital technology figured in the lives of older adults during periods of social isolation. 146 people aged between 65 and 91 completed their survey between May and July 2020, with 23 of them (aged between 65 and 89) also agreeing to take part in follow-up interviews. The majority of them (60.9%) were women, 47.5% were Black or African American, and 43.5% were White. Richards et al. found that older adults demonstrated resilience and creativity in adapting to social distancing measures, successfully maintaining social connections both in person and online. As in the study of Ray et al. (2022) above, many intended to sustain some of the lifestyle changes they had adopted during the pandemic, including spending more time at home and taking up new hobbies. While some participants mentioned that they were not good with technology, 54.1% of them nevertheless persisted in learning new skills while socially distancing. Of the survey respondents who tried out new things, a chief motivating force was connecting with friends and family (73%). Others used digital technology to access telehealth services (27%), entertainment (23%), and online shopping (7%). As many participants in this study were regular church-goers, many, including some aged over-75, learnt new digital skills to keep up with church-based activities that moved online during lockdown (e.g. Zoom and other video technologies). However, while most participants reported they used existing technology devices more during the pandemic (e.g. cell phones, computers, TVs, and tablets), fewer were keen to adopt new ones, finding getting acquainted with them difficult and frustrating.

Focusing on **Canada**, the Canadian Internet Use Survey of 2022 shows that internet use among Canadians aged 15 years and older reached 95% in 2020, up 3% from 2020. However, among Canadians aged 75 years and older, internet use increased from 62% in 2020 to 72% in 2022. Sixsmith et al. (2022) analysed data from two independent cross-sectional surveys completed online or via computer-assisted telephone interview by adults over the age of 65 in 2019 and 2020 to better understand their attitudes and behaviours regarding digital technology. 51% of these respondents were female, and their geographical distribution aligned with the proportional representation of the population. Of the 996 respondents to the 2019 survey, 777 were aged 65 to 74 of age and 219 were aged 75 or above. In 2020, of 927 survey respondents 631 were between 65 and 74 years old and 296 were 75 years old or above. Comparing these data sets, Sixsmith et al. found that in terms of internet use, only slightly more older adults in the 2020 sample (88%) reported using the internet daily compared to 2019 (86%). However, smartphone ownership in the 65 to 75 age group had increased from 62.0% in 2019 to 72.1% in the same time span. Concerning the ownership of desktops, laptops, tablets, video game consoles, wearable devices, voice assistant devices, or assistive robots, there only a slight but not significant increase. The use of internet-enabled TV increased from 31.3% in 2019 to 47.7% in 2020, while the use of daily wearable health devices increased from only 69.4% in 2019 to 80.1% in 2020. It would be interesting to know whether this large increase in the use of wearable health devices was due to more such products coming onto the market, and increase in health concerns connected to the pandemic, or both.

While the use of landline phone calls in Canada decreased over the period under investigation, that of video calls via computer or smartphone significantly increased: from 11.3% (65 to 74 year-olds) and 11.1% (75

years plus) respectively in 2019 to 16.2% (65 to 74 year-olds) and 22.3% (75 years plus) respectively in 2020. Many respondents also reported their use of digital services like online shopping for essential items (61%) and non-essential items (48%), webinars (51%), online social activities (50%), online streaming (46%), food delivery: not groceries (45%), social media (42%), networking apps (42%), physical activity tracker (19%), voice-assisted technology (18%), meditation app (18%), task scheduler (17%), wearable device (17%), online financial tools (16%), and smart home tech (15%) had increased. Moreover, most older adults (>68%) intended to continue using these technologies post-pandemic.

In **Australia**, Asadi et al. (2023) considered how older adults experienced the speed of life during the pandemic and how this impacted on their relations to technology. The Australian Government's Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (2025) has estimated that just in the first eight weeks of the COVID-19 crisis, Australia "vaulted forward five years in consumer and business digital adoption." How did the pandemic and the rapid digitalisation that followed it impact older adults' relationship with technology? To answer these questions, Asadi et. al. carried out two to three rounds of semi-structured online or telephone interviews with 13 older adults aged between 65 and 85, none of whom lived in a nursing home. The first round of interviews took place during the May to June 2020 lockdown, the second during August 2020, just after lockdown, and the third during October 2021. Regarding technology use, during the May to June 2020 round of interviews, all participants reported that the devices they used most were either laptops or desktop computers, which they used for at least an hour every day. However, some spent all their waking hours online. Although most participants had privacy concerns regarding digital technology, they felt quite comfortable and capable of using it and tried to

keep up with new developments like Zoom. In August 2020, all participants were still using the devices and apps they had become familiar with during the first lockdown, although one participant was concerned that some of his friends were beginning to fall behind advances in technology.

One finding of Asadi et al.'s study was that many study participants experienced time as slowing down during the pandemic. They explained this in terms of having more time to spend on activities and tasks, and more free time as they had fewer social activities to attend. Some reported using this extra time to consider what technologies they would need for a socially distanced life. Two bought more recent smartphones models and one a new laptop, while another one upgraded his data plan. However, despite many participants agreeing that technology was useful during lockdown, some were frustrated by learning new software and online social networks. Many found social media 'banal', preferring deeper social interactions in smaller social circles. They also found that certain activities that enabled people to make friends and form bonds were simply not replicable by technology, such as gardening clubs, which were important to older adults here. This highlights limitations of digital technology that we also discovered in our empirical work, where there were strong views that technology should not act as a 'stand in' for people, or that it should not 'replace' (e.g. in contexts of care). To address these issues, Asadi et al recommend that designers work with users when designing technologies aimed at a 'slow life', to ensure technology speaks to *their* needs and desires.

3.2. Digital Exclusion and the Digital Divide

Across **OECD countries**, a number of reasons have been identified for variations in internet usage in 2019, including age, lack of digital skills, and

gender differences (OECD, 2020). The fact that age as a barrier to engagement with digital technology often intersects with a lack of digital skills was highlighted by data collected across all **EU member states** in 2023 (Eurostat 2023). This showed that only 33% of people aged between 55 and 74 years had basic digital skills compared to 80% of people aged between 16 and 35 years old. In an increasingly digitalised world, this can have serious consequences, as data collected as part of the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA) in the **UK** and our empirical study have shown.

For example, ELSA data found that the pandemic made accessing medical appointments, support services, and consumer activities worse for the digitally excluded, thereby “further exacerbating the negative health impact of the pandemic, increasing isolation and loneliness, and social exclusion” (Wallinheimo and Evans, 2022: 7). Malkowski et al. (2024)’s analysis of ELSA data showed that during the pandemic, increased internet use in the **UK** was also uneven due to socio-economic factors, which influenced who benefitted from digital technology and who did not. For example, older adults with a higher education and adequate financial resources were more likely to participate in a wider range of online activities than those from lower socio-economic backgrounds, who were more at risk from digital exclusion. These findings show that age is only one dimension of digital exclusion, a condition which, as Malkowski et al. (ibid.) have found, exacerbated loneliness and mental health problems during the pandemic.

Focusing on health, a policy brief published by the **World Health Organisation (WHO) / European Union (EU)** Observatory on Health Systems and Policy (2021) in which the use of digital health tools in EU

member states before, during and after the pandemic was assessed also confirmed that the costs and benefits of digital health were unequally distributed. It recommended that to ensure that vulnerable groups (e.g. lower income groups, older adults, and people facing language and cultural barriers) have equal access to digital technology, extra support needs to be made available for patients with physical and/or mental impairment, especially regarding digital tools people use for self-examination. The brief also emphasised that “Community organizations and community health workers may play a key role in providing training for older adults and other marginalized groups” (ibid.: 15), bringing us back to the intersection of age and the lack of digital skills in digital exclusion.

While a primary focus of policy during the pandemic was on removing limitations to the uptake of digital health tools, the WHO/EU noted that it was now equally important to develop “policies and practices that can be put in place to create an enabling and supportive environment for the expanded use of digital health tools.” (ibid.: 27). This requires strategic investment that targets “both the development of infrastructure within the health setting and outside (e.g. internet provision), and research and development to ensure that technologies continue to evolve.” In conclusion, the WHO/EU noted that a better understanding of digital inequalities across all population groups and strategies to tackle are urgently needed.

In a study carried out by the charity Age UK in the **UK**, it was found that 25% of 65-plus-year-olds were still off the Internet and lacked essential digital skills, thereby risking exclusion from essential digital health and other services increasingly only provided online (e.g. banking and shopping) (Age UK, 2023). Also focusing on the **UK**, Clayton et al. (2023) interviewed 11

older disabled adults who were socially distancing during the early COVID-19 lockdowns and their support workers to explore how digital technology (provided by a national charity after a local council service was decommissioned) helped them cope with the pandemic. They also investigated the importance of tech support. Eight of their participants were visually impaired; four had a physical disability (primarily musculoskeletal in nature); two had hearing problems, and three had a combination of disabilities. All participants used a broad range of equipment, including desktop computers, laptops, tablets and iPads, Smart mobile phones, and voice-activated technology such as Amazon Echo (Alexa) and Google Home. They were familiar with speech recognition software, text readers, audiobooks, YouTube, Zoom, Skype, and online banking and shopping.

Regarding the benefits participants derived from using these technologies, the study found that tools like video calling helped them cope with the loss of social contact resulting from physical distancing. Due to their disabilities, some participants were already used to a certain level of isolation and loneliness, and for them, a key benefit of digital technology was that it provided them with new opportunities for taking part in leisure activities as well as enabling them to keep in touch with family and friends. Several participants mentioned that they had gained more confidence in using digital technology during lockdown and had enjoyed activities like obtaining online information and doing online shopping. Those who used digital technology for creative purposes used it to make art, music, poetry, photography, and to keep a diary. Regarding entertainment, many watched videos online, played computer games, and listened to audiobooks and music. This helped them deal with the stress and anxiety caused by the pandemic.

However, some participants found increased technology use challenging and encountered accessibility issues due to their conditions and disabilities. Especially those who were visually impaired and/or struggled with dexterity required specialised equipment and software. This highlights the exclusionary potential of digital technology based on health issues. Many participants thought computers were “complicated” and were overwhelmed by their “jargon”, and in our research, flagged up the pace of digitalisation as an issue. The support workers interviewed by Clayton et al., on the other hand, commented on the rapid increase in demand for tech advice and support during the pandemic, which they could only provide remotely. This was challenging for them and prevented them from delivering the benefits they could in person. In some cases, increased online support also led to a dependency relationship, where some clients were reluctant to leave the service.

A cross-sectional survey conducted in **Denmark** online or on paper investigated the use of mHealth applications (smartphones or tablets designed to collect health data, monitor well-being, and assist with various health-related activities for individuals) before (n=315) and after (n=501) the pandemic (van Elburg et al., 2023). Participants had to have no cognitive impairment, be above the age of 65, and live either independently or in a senior living facility. It is noteworthy that prior to the pandemic, half of all older adults in Denmark had no intention to use mHealth applications, and this study found that despite the significant barriers created to accessing health care by the pandemic, participants' willingness to adopt mHealth reflected this. As a result, the authors concluded that targeted and dedicated policies would be needed in Denmark to encourage older adults to engage with mHealth technology, providing adequate support and digital skills training.

In a study conducted in **Portugal**, Diehl et al. (2022) also found that their ten participants, aged between 70 and 77, even though most of them stated that they had a medium to high degree of digital technology usage and were more or less comfortable with handling digital technologies, heavily relied on the help of family members to use digital technology, including for sustaining basic tablet functionalities like video conferencing. This corroborates our own findings that many older adults are highly dependent on family members and others for technical support. The flip side of this, as highlighted by Diehl et al., is that people with less locally available family support often struggle to use digital technology and are at increased risk of digital exclusion. During the pandemic, this situation became worse, and Diehl et al. (2022) recommended that increased government support, the provision of a good digital infrastructure, easy access, and digital skills training would be required to address this. They also highlighted the importance of taking a social justice approach to policy development aimed at digital inclusion.

To find out how rapid digitalisation caused by the pandemic impacted older adults in the **US and Canada**, an anonymous, cross-sectional survey of 1,405 people aged 18 and above that included 132 people over the age of 65 was conducted online by Blackman et al. (2023) in June 2020, the majority of whom identified as female, well-educated, and White. Echoing findings from other countries, Blackman et al. found that age impacted digital technology use, with older adults struggling more to adapt to online services- and resources provision (such as doctor appointments) than did their younger counterparts. The older respondents were, the less they also relied on social media to obtain information about COVID-19, preferring newspapers and radios as information-sources instead. This corroborates findings from our UK-focused study. Based on their findings, Blackman et al.

recommended that service providers need to make more effort to assist older adults with the digital transformation, providing adequate internet services and supporting digital skills training. Furthermore, they highlighted that these efforts should be coordinated between individuals, communities and policy.

The important role that family members and friends play in helping older adults gain digital skills was also highlighted in the **US**, in a study conducted by Richards et al. (2021). This found that 53% of the older adults who completed their survey (n146) and participated in interviews (n23) had learnt digital skills from family members or friends, including texting, making video calls, playing online, and doing online shopping. However, digital exclusion here appeared not to be simply caused by a lack of skills. As another **US** study showed, digital exclusion is an intersectional problem. According to the National Health and Ageing Trends Study (NHATS) COVID-19 supplemental mail survey, analysed by Drazich et al. in 2023, older adults under economic strain significantly decreased their use of technology-based personal communication during the pandemic compared to those with adequate financial resources. Unsurprising, low-income adults were also less likely to own a computer or have broadband at home.

The impacts of rapid digitisation during the pandemic on older adults were also studied in **British Columbia, Canada**, by Sin et al. (2021), who interviewed 24 older adults aged 65 and above from diverse backgrounds. This study found that where in-person support was prevented by social distancing rules, the digital divide became more pronounced. Although many participants adopted new technologies and learnt new digital skills during the pandemic, others fell behind due to the loss of in-person technology support

and age-related discrimination, the latter reducing their opportunities for digital engagement. "Ageism" refers to stereotyping, prejudice, and discrimination against older adults, and Sin et al.'s study provides detailed examples of how ageism affected their participants' engagement with digital technology. For example, several participants explained how they were excluded from taking part in online, Zoom-based, activities due to ageism. Even older adults themselves (e.g. senior leadership group members) held ageist sentiments, describing other older adults as "slow" or "uninterested" in taking part in online activities. Sin et al. concluded that not only is ageism widespread, but it has also been internalised by older adults, exacerbating its negative effects. Ageism can have profound consequences for those affected by it, as Sin et al. found. It can cause feelings of frustration, anxiety, and alienation. The fact that older adults during the pandemic were homogeneously portrayed as frail and helpless has further exacerbated ageism, today a serious and widespread problem. Sin et al. emphasised the urgent need for more research on this topic, also calling for more in-person support to reduce technology-related social exclusion where older adults can play an important role as advocates of digital technology.

In another study carried out in **Ontario, Canada**, Zapletal et al. (2023) found that in follow-up interviews with 12 older adults who had previously self-identified as "occasional or non-users" of digital technology, the pandemic had increased the digital divide. On the other hand, for participants whose experience of digital technology increased during the pandemic, it benefitted them by helping them feel less isolated.

Zhao et al. (2023), in their study of 40 independently living older adults in **Victoria, Australia**, found that although older adults felt forced to

adopt digital technologies during lockdown, not being able to obtain in-person technical support made it harder for them to learn how to use the, reducing their opportunities for social interaction. Some of Zhao et al.'s participants adapted to this by learning how to solve technology-related problems online or by forming meaningful online connections with others. This led the authors to conclude that the adoption of digital technologies during COVID-19 could both support *and* undermine older adults' autonomy, competence, and social relationships.

As these studies from around the world show, digital exclusion is a complex, intersectional challenge that will require equally complex socio-economic policies to be addressed and the involvement of many different actors at many different levels to be successfully tackled. As the negative impacts of digital exclusion can be significant and digitalisation continues apace, urgent steps need to be taken by governments, industry, and communities around the world to forestall them whilst alternatives to digital should continue to be made available.

While studies in **Singapore** showed that for its younger population, age, gender, and education were critical influencing factors in decision-making processes around the use of the online platforms provided by the Government during Covid-19, Perdana and Mokhtar (2022) - in a study involving 144 older adults aged 60 years and above - found that social influences (family, friends, peers) and perceived ease of use and benefits to be derived from the platforms were key motivating factors here for their use. Social support was found to be particularly important in increasing the participation rate of seniors in virtual events here. For the further development of such event platforms, Perdana and Mokhtar, therefore,

recommended that policymakers communicate and collaborate with social service agencies to understand what motivates seniors to use them. For the design of *national* digital technology policies and initiatives, the authors advised the Government to collaborate with agencies and practitioners and to involve seniors in co-design.

3.3. Concerns Raised by Rapid Digitalisation

3.3.1. Mental Health and Well-Being

Increased internet use during the pandemic in **OECD countries** led to the OECD expressing concern that people were spending too much time online. In 2020, it therefore urged member states to “seize this opportunity to address the diverse range of social issues that the digital transformation raises, including questions around data-driven healthcare, disinformation and screen addiction” (OECD, 2020: 5).

Results from data collected as part of the **English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA)** on internet use and its impacts on the mental health of older adults during the COVID-19 pandemic in the **UK** (Malkowski et al., 2024) confirmed that internet usage among seniors increased, particularly for activities such as communication, staying up-to-date (news), and managing everyday tasks. This helped some of them feel less isolated as it enabled them to maintain social ties and access crucial health information, thereby improving their mental health during lockdown periods. For those with limited digital access, however, ELSA data showed that the shift towards online services made feelings of anxiety and isolation worse. Nimrod (2020), also based on ELSA data, found that the rapid digitalisation

spurred by the pandemic also led older adults suffer from increased “technostress,” i.e. stress experienced as a result of increased technology usage. These findings suggest that more research is needed on internet usage and mental health and well-being.

Focusing on **England**, Balki et al. (2023) looked at the impacts of digital technology usage on 25 older adults in the northwest of **England**. They found that 72% of participants reported digital technology as having a negative impact on their well-being, with Facebook particularly being singled out as causing increased anxiety due to the volume of news about the pandemic it fed participants on their newsfeeds. As a result, many stopped using Facebook over time. Some participants also reported feeling lonelier as a result of using digital technology because staying in touch virtually made them miss seeing loved ones in person even more.

In **Portugal**, on the other hand, Diehl et al. (2022) found that respondents questioned the benefits of mHealth technologies because they led to a reduction in human contact. This made participants doubt whether they wanted to continue using mHealth technologies post-pandemic.

The **US-focused** National Health and Aging Trends Study’s (NHATS) COVID-19 supplemental mail survey, answered by 3,188 participants, found that regarding the impact of digital technology on people’s mental health, better mental health was associated here with *less* technology-based activity during the pandemic, indicating that many consider technology as having harmful effects on older adults here. Better older adult mental health was generally not associated by survey participants with technology-based

activities, but negatively associated with technology-based communication (Drazich et al., 2023: 7).

Sixsmith et al. (2022), who compared 996 responses received to a 2019 survey to 777 responses received to a 2020 survey on attitudes and behaviours concerning digital technology from older adults aged 65 and above in **Canada**, found that when asked if they agreed or disagreed that technological advancements could help with aspects of healthy ageing like managing ageing, staying active/safe/in own home/independent, and prolonging life, significantly fewer in 2020 compared to 2019 agreed. However, a significantly greater proportion of respondents in 2020 compared to 2019 agreed that technological advances could reduce social isolation (Sixsmith et al. 2022:21). This led Sixsmith et al. to conclude that while many older adults in Canada appear to have adapted quite well to the rapid digitalisation that occurred here during the pandemic, the longer-term impacts of this have yet to be established.

In **Australia**, Asadi et al. (2022) found that as the pandemic progressed, some of their study participants became increasingly concerned about the negative impacts that digitalisation had on socialising and communication, with many believing that texting or emailing prevented deeper, more personal conversations. Although participants appreciated that activities like church services, garden clubs, and bridge games had moved online, they missed face-to-face interactions. Some who were less mobile and had greater physical needs, however, were happy to maintain virtual contacts with friends after the lockdown, as for them, this mitigated over-exertion.

In **Saudi Arabia**, 397 older adults participated in a survey and 5 older adults in an online interview conducted as part of a study that looked at the experience of older adults and their families with the mandatory pandemic mobile tracking applications introduced during the pandemic (Alharbi et al., 2021). According to IDI ranking data², 86.2% of households in Saudi Arabia have computers. Of the 13.8 % of households without a computer, most are in rural areas, have a limited income, and lack the desire to own a computer. However, although 99% of households with a computer have internet access, only 95.7% of them use the Internet. According to Saad and Fahim (2021), this is due to “two main reasons: lack of skills and high cost of the Internet subscription compared with level income” (Saad and Fahim, 2021). Alharbi et al.’s participants were aged between 60 and 92 years, with 80% of them living with their families, who were also present at the one-on-one interviews. 69% of them were regular smartphone users.

The study found that older users generally struggled with using the tracking technologies provided by themselves, becoming more dependent on others for help as a result. They also reported finding the number of restrictions and technologies that they had to get acquainted with in a short period of time overwhelming. This negatively impacted on their physical and mental well-being.

² The ICT Development Index (IDI) is a composite index that combines 11 indicators into one benchmark measure that can be used to monitor and compare developments in information and communication technology (ICT) between countries and over time. They include five indicators called Access sub-index that are used to measure ICT readiness, including fixed telephone subscriptions, mobile-cellular telephone subscriptions, and international Internet bandwidth per internet user, households with a computer, and households with Internet access.

3.3.2. *Cybersecurity*

Increased internet use has long been shown to raised concerns about online safety among older adults, who have been shown to be prone to cyberattacks and scams (Age UK, 2019; McDonald and Mentis, 2023). These concerns are far from unfounded, as World Health Organisation (WHO) European Union (**EU**) Observatory on Health Systems Policy brief published in 2021 has highlighted, stressing the fact that privacy issues were still inadequately addressed by the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) at the time.

In a study conducted in the northwest of **England** by Balki et al. (2023) involving 25 older adults, 72% were concerned about privacy and security issues, with concerns being expressed about the misuse of personal information posted online, the safety of online banking, identity theft, fraud, and online bullying. Cybersecurity was also a concern in our empirical study involving 40 older adults, discussed below.

To protect older adults from the risk of cyberattacks in **England**, an innovative approach was developed to provide them with security information during the pandemic. Fourteen older adults were trained and supported in 2020 as "CyberGuardians" (community cybersecurity educators) as part of a nine-month-long community-driven cybersecurity initiative involving Newcastle University and non-academic partners working with older adult communities. These guardians used Facebook and email to pass on security tips and warnings to around 820 other older adults during the pandemic (a previous poster and phone call campaign to raise cybersecurity awareness had failed). The success of the initiative was traced to an "embedded peer-to-peer information dissemination strategy, rather

than expert-to-citizen, facilitating the inclusion of individuals who would ordinarily be unlikely to seek cybersecurity information” (Nicholson et al. 2021: 2).

In **Portugal**, Diehl et al. (2022) also found that the ten older adults they interviewed between 2020 and 2021 were concerned about privacy and security matters, here regarding social networks and online banking.

In their study of how older adults experienced the introduction of online conferencing tools during the COVID-19 pandemic in the **US**, Ray et.al. (2022) discovered that during the early stages of adoption, most of the 25 people aged between 60 and 89 years old from an independent/assisted community they interviewed were chiefly concerned about communication effectiveness and the success of social interactions. For example, they found that where conversations were held in more formal settings, participants’ anxiety about their personal appearance or the appearance of their physical background increased, with people worrying about whether the room they used for online meetings was well-lit and undisturbed, which was associated with “being professional” and/or “polite”. Over time, however, higher-level privacy concerns took over. Participants began to worry about dealing with uninvited attendees who might use aliases, about meetings being recorded without their consent, and about the cloud storage of recorded meetings. Nineteen participants also had privacy and security concerns about online tools. Regarding online medical appointments and financial appointments, for example, Ray et al. found that most participants felt comfortable and “safe” when sharing information with professionals they regularly dealt with, but not when communicating with “strangers”. Some explained that regarding online communication in medical contexts, reassurance from their doctors would make them feel more comfortable.

All 13 participants in the study conducted by Asadi et al. (2022) with older adults in **Australia** were also concerned about privacy issues associated with internet-connected technologies. The three participants who used smart assistants (e.g. Alexa or Google Home) to check on the weather or add items to their grocery list all felt that the assistants invaded their privacy. As a result, they were uncomfortable with using them.

Similarly, in another study of 40 independently living older adults and their use of digital technology for engaging in meaningful activities during the COVID-19 lockdown restrictions in **Victoria, Australia**, Zhao et al. (2023) found that excessive, irrelevant information and privacy and security concerns undermined confidence in technology use here.

3.3.3. Product-Related Safety Concerns

The speed at which digitalisation unfolded during the pandemic and has continued to do so has led to concerns about the safety of technologies released on the market. For example, the **World Health Organisation (WHO)** identified gaps in evidence on the impact, efficacy and cost-effectiveness of many mHealth tools released during the pandemic and expressed concern about their impacts on patients and health professionals (WHO and EU Observatory on Health Systems and Policy Brief, 2021). Many of the tools released do not comply with EU guidelines for Responsible Research and Innovation, which require upstream engagement and foresight studies of potential consequences. To address this, the WHO has recommended rapid reviews and evaluations of current digital health tools and their use, benefits and problems with the aim of creating an evidence

base for “what to continue in the future as well as what adaptations are required” (WHO/EU Observatory on Health Systems Policy brief, 2021: 8).

4. FINDINGS – EMPIRICAL STUDY

Following iterative cycles of thematic data analysis, a number of themes were identified relating to how the COVID-19 pandemic and rapid digitalisation impacted older adults. These overlap with many of the themes raised by the studies carried out in different countries discussed above. Here, we present our empirical findings, showing how digital technology usage changed due to the pandemic, focusing on shopping, banking, participating in social activities, and healthcare. We consider the emotional and social aspects that digitalisation gave rise to, as mentioned by participants. Finally, we look at comments made about confidence and its role in the use of digital technology – what can boost it and what undermines it.

4.1. Digital Technology Usage: Before, During and After the Pandemic

For participants who were already reasonably confident in using technology pre-pandemic (for example, in using email and other communication media, running Google searches, or doing word processing), technology usage during the pandemic was reported as remaining broadly similar: “*the same old because I already was doing a lot*” [R1_F1], one participant commented, a view echoed by another who said “*there wasn't*

any great need... there wasn't any reason to do anything different to what I did." [R2_M2].

Others, however, felt forced by the pandemic to adopt digital technologies, and for some, this led to a notable increase in digital technology use. For example participant R2_F8 thought that the pandemic had *"made us have to use it more. It's forced along a path that would probably [...] have been a bit further back... [...]. Which was in response to the lockdown, really. It was the only way forward [...] to use digital technology more."* This view was shared by many, especially regarding online shopping, explored below.

4.1.1 Online Shopping

Regarding forced adoption, one participant explained that due to the pandemic, she *"didn't have a means of shopping really, because [...] I'd always shopped in person. I've never wanted to shop online."* [R2_F5]. This view was echoed by another participant who felt that she *"had to [start doing online shopping] during COVID [but didn't] like shopping online. I don't mind buying things for the house [...] or the garden.... But I'm not keen on buying clothes online...."* [R1_F6]. Someone else said she *"didn't even use it initially during the first COVID lockdown [...] [But] then there was the second one in the January after Christmas and I thought, [name redacted], it's time you learned this click-and-collect at Sainsbury's. I'm not going to risk getting COVID now having come through so many months without it, and also when you become... an even older lady who can't get out, you need to know how this works, so I used it. I didn't really like it, but I used it [...]."* [R1_F7]. It is noteworthy that all these participants stated that they disliked

online shopping, but embarked on it for lack of an alternative. As participant R2_F8 explained, *"During the pandemic, if you wanted a birthday present, you just sort of went [taps on table], [...] and got it delivered to your door. Well, ... you couldn't go and browse anymore, could you?"* For some participants, only being able to do shopping online during the pandemic had long-lasting consequences, with one noting: *"I very rarely go into town now. Very rarely."* [R1_F7].

If given a choice, most participants stated they preferred shopping in person to online shopping. Some noted that it could be cumbersome, with several noting the lack of slots or the inability to register with supermarkets as a barrier: *"I wanted to shop online, but I couldn't get one because I was, I was very late [in realising lockdown was coming, meaning the demand for online shopping outstripped the capacity to deliver] [...] ... when other countries started to lockdown, I still didn't really think, 'oh, well, how are we going to manage,' really."* [R2_F5]. Another explained that only pick-up slots were available when lockdowns began: *"So I think we couldn't get deliveries when it started. So we ordered pick-ups."* But things didn't always go smoothly, and *"there were two traumatic moments when ... an order got lost online or something, you know, but we survived... I remember getting quite worked up about it for a while"* [R1_M1].

Some participants explained that the lack of choice offered in online shopping resulted in their abandoning it: *"They only had about 300 items on the list and, and about half of that was alcohol and, you know, things that you're not going to be, well, I'm not buying all the time. And there was hardly any vegetables and I don't know, I mean, I did it for a few weeks and just got so really fed up with it, really, because there wasn't much choice."* [R2_F5]. Another took advantage of a dedicated "senior hour" at her usual supermarket: *"the items that you could click and collect weren't necessarily*

the items I wanted. Or the items I wanted weren't on the click and collect... I like to select certain things. And so I began to go ... very early in the morning, ... in the hour for senior people. And I just kept that up." [R2_F6].

One participant chose 'click and collect' option for shopping rather than the delivery one to retain a sense of normality during lockdown: *"I picked things up rather than them deliver because then I could go out in the car and, and, you know, have a life really"*. [R2_F7]. Several other participants who were proficient at using technology also emphasised their choosing not to online shop, primarily due to reasons of wanting to maintain community: *"I didn't start online shopping. I still wanted to actually go into shops. I actually do very little online shopping. That's the one thing I don't do, whatever. As a matter of principle, I want shops."* [R2_F10]. Another, who continued going into work during the pandemic observed: *"I didn't rush to online shopping because I don't want online shopping. So I kept with going in and I'd rather queue up outside than queue up on a thingy and then wait for a slot."* [R2_M2].

A number of participants who were less confident with using technology were grateful that they had support from family, friends and neighbours with food shopping: *"In COVID, well within two hours, I would think, in lockdown, we had six neighbours knocking on the door, "Can we do anything for you? Can we do your shopping? Can we—", you know, etcetera. I was thrilled to bits with these really good neighbours... So I never needed it [online shopping]."* [R1_F8]. Someone whose shopping was done and delivered by her son and daughter similarly emphasised how she appreciated that as a result, she *"got to see somebody and talk to somebody sometime."* [R2_F1]. Others, living in a village outside the town, had food delivered for them from local firms: *"we were lucky in the respect, [...] we've*

got a butcher who [brings?] meat out for us [...] we have a milkman. Well, he... had eggs, cheese and potatoes. And you name it, he has it." [R2_F4].

Many participants used online shopping for non-food items during the pandemic, either independently or through family, and were generally satisfied with it as a service, with one highlighting that her continuing use of online shopping meant that she rarely shopped in town now: *"I didn't use Amazon really again until COVID, when you kind of had to. And since then, I buy constantly online [...] which I would never have done. [...] I very rarely go into town now."* [R1_F7]. Another explained that she *"did order some things online [through Amazon]. [...] [M]ainly erm various household items that I couldn't get otherwise, [...] not food items so much. [...] I ordered Amazon Books as well."* [R2_F6].

The majority of participants showed resilience in being able to get what shopping they needed during the pandemic, primarily following their own preferences as to whether they achieved this through online shopping (conducted independently or using family members as proxies), going into shops with masks, being supported by neighbours, family and friends bringing items to them, or some combination of these. One participant's lack of experience with technology, combined with serious illness and covid-related circumstances in her family, negatively impacted her life in this scenario, resulting in her needing to rely on social services to have food delivered and leaving her feeling isolated.

4.1.2 Online Banking

Most participants who used online banking had already got online accounts set up before COVID-19 broke out, for others, however, the pandemic acted as a motivating force. Participant R2_F6 explained that *"I*

was using the laptop and the iPad prior to lock down. But certainly, I did begin to use it more because of lockdown, especially with online banking, because [name of bank] have been trying to get me to go online banking for quite a bit and I refused. But during lockdown, I thought, well, I, I, I better try and do this because I might need to do it for various reasons." This participant also stated that she had continued using technologies she had learnt how to use during lockdown, but that her technology usage as a whole had not increased: *"It stayed about the same. Say the things I learned to do during lockdown, I'm sort of continuing with."* While banking was often raised as an issue during interviews, it was rarely in connection with the pandemic. One participant stated that he had found it convenient being able to pay into his wife's house-keeping account during the pandemic: *"without anybody needing to go in the bank."* [R2_M3].

4.1.3 Video Conferencing

Regarding video-conferencing, 15 participants specifically mentioned the need to learn Zoom during the pandemic to enable them to participate in activities. Zoom became a popular way to interact with other people and take up new hobbies. Our research showed that Zoom was used for many different purposes and that people responded quite differently to it. Participant R2_F9, for example, told us how she attended two funerals via Zoom, which she felt was *"better than nothing,"* although she would have preferred to be there in person: *"We did two funerals like that... Yeah. Just clicked on the web link and yeah, yeah, it wasn't ideal, but... the access was there. [...] [You] just had to be adapted for these circumstances. [...] Not as good as being there, but yeah better than nothing..."* [R2_F9].

Most participants had led busy lives pre-pandemic, reporting participating in various activities including volunteering, membership of special interest groups (e.g. local history or politics, singing in choirs), looking after grandchildren, taking on roles in local community centres and churches, and so on. One participant, R2_M3, described his experience of using Zoom to host meetings of local 'University of the Third Age' (U3A) groups which he had been chairing in person pre-pandemic, acknowledging that he found it more difficult with certain people *"to shut them up online"* as he was unable to use facial/hand gestures as effectively. Nevertheless, he emphasised the importance of maintaining continuity for people during this period, *"So we kept as many groups going as possible."* Indeed, he said, they *"were actually getting more people on the Zoom meetings than were on... the actual physical meetings."* Noting that physical attendance had not returned to pre-pandemic levels, he suggested that older people may have *"got out of the habit"* of going out at night. This suggests that the pandemic might have had long-lasting impacts on older adults that need to be further researched. A comment we received from another respondent about how she struggled to go shopping after having been in isolation for so long suggests that readjusting to post-pandemic times has not been easy for some older adults (see under "shopping" above and "social and emotional aspects" below).

Concerns about Zoom were raised by a number of people who disliked online meetings and thought they were far removed from, and inferior to, face-to-face meetings. This was the case for participant R1_F8, who, with reference to her singing at church observed: *"I'm not happy with Zoom. I did join in but singing in your bedroom on your own, 'cause it's in, in the little bedroom, it's not like being part of a group and, and then if you had a chat afterwards, it was to everybody, it wasn't to just a few. "* [R1_F8].

Another participant described how the meetings of a society he was involved in on Zoom felt “sterile”, raising important aspect of face-to-face communication that he felt were lost on Zoom:

*“Oh God yes, that’s, that’s been the consequence of lockdown.... that the, the [name of Society] went on Zoom and it’s just awful, awful, awful. It’s like being a rabbit in a pet shop. And you have to hold your paw up so you can speak and it meant that certain people, particularly the person who was administering the Zoom, had the power just to ignore you and so you couldn’t speak, whereas in an ordinary meeting, before, you get to the meeting early and you start making alliances with people that you want to, you know, do you want them to support certain things you want to say, so you’ve got them on board. During the meeting, you can have an aside [gestures to show talking behind hand] like, “Isn’t he talking b*lllocks”. Which you can’t do on, on, on a Zoom. And then after the meeting you can do all the networking [...]. You can’t do that in a Zoom, you just, you’re just there and you just sit there”.*
[R2_M1].

Those with a certain level of technological expertise and access tried out new activities, including online courses, during the pandemic, which they enjoyed: “... I did a couple of courses on Zoom. Both of them art ones, one with the Royal Academy and one with the National Gallery. Yeah, they were really good. And actually the National Gallery one is still continuing, which is, which is great.” [R1_F9]. Another, while enjoying the online course undertaken, did not particularly like using Zoom because of a negative experience with it during one of the meetings: “[...] I’m not keen on [...] Zoom meetings. I know how to do it. I worked it out during COVID cause I needed to. [...] I did an art therapy thing, which I really enjoyed. It was good. But when it got to the bit where you had to sort of speak back, I didn’t

press the button to engage. I didn't engage with it. So they couldn't see me." [R1_F6].

Regarding continued usage, one participant, who had been shown how to use Zoom during the pandemic, commented that her usage has continued post-pandemic, including running a U3A group using Zoom: *"I do use Zoom and I know how to do it. I do use Zoom because we then started using it for the U3A Spanish class that I go to, and I was also running a German group with U3A and we started doing that on Zoom. That has now gone back to face-to-face contact. Yeah, but I still use Zoom for all kinds of things... there's a, a university's German link. So I now go to quite a lot of Zoom lectures. I even went to one in Australia via Zoom!"* [R2_F6]

In contrast, another participant highlighted that hearing issues around background noise meant that *"Zoom meetings just became a, a buzz and being stressful, and I didn't like them..."* [R2_F9]. For the participant who had used Zoom for attending U3A courses, she had stopped doing so post-pandemic because she no longer found courses that interested her [R1_F7].

4.1.4 Digital Technology for Health-Related Purposes

Of those participants who used apps for health-related purposes, many described using apps provided by their doctors' surgery. The majority used them to order repeat prescriptions, mentioning convenience as the key driver: *"I've had the app a long time."* [R2_F9], and *"I was able to reorder my tablets using Patient Access [app], so I just reordered on the computer... the chemist will text me when the prescription's ready."* [R2_M3]

No participant mentioned being able to book appointments with their GP through the app, with one observing that this functionality did not currently exist. Most participants had registered themselves to use the app prior to the pandemic, with a few mentioning they had to go into the surgery in person to get it set up properly. Several participants, including those proficient in using digital technologies, phoned or walked to their medical centre to make appointments/order prescriptions *"Yeah, cause I always telephone, you know? Yeah. I know they try and get you to use an app and what have you, but I don't have one. So I use the telephone, [laughs] you know."* [R2_F3]. A number, particularly those aged over 80 who did not use digital technologies, relied on family to liaise with their surgeries and to make appointments on their behalf: *"My daughter, my daughters are quite up with all this technology. So if I've got any appointments, say I want something urgent, they will do it for me, you know?"* [R2_F4] and *"Actually our [name of daughter] used to do all that. She got them to phone her about everything so she knew I didn't, I didn't have to."* [R2_F1].

4.2 Mental Health and Well-Being

A few participants, all of whom had little experience of using digital technologies, described how isolated they felt during lockdown: *"It was hell at the beginning because I don't like my own company... A lot of us, yeah, lost two years. I was vulnerable, couldn't go out. I just moved to a new flat."* [R1_F5]. One participant in her 90s described how living through the pandemic had aged her, and how this had impacted her life post-pandemic: *"COVID made me old. It aged me, a lot of people have said it. Yes, it did. It aged me a lot. Yeah, because I lost, how long was it on for? ... However long it was, I didn't, I didn't go out, so I didn't mix with people. I didn't go to*

shops. So after that I went into a [supermarket], with my daughter-in-law [...]. I walked down the first aisle and I couldn't get any further. I froze. And so she came back. "What's the matter?" And I said "I can't see anything. I can't, I just can't go any further." "You stay there." So she brought things to me." [R1_F4].

Interestingly, several participants, all of whom were experienced technology users, did not appear to find the pandemic particularly burdensome, with some suggesting that they had actually "enjoyed it":

"Well, I think by, by the time COVID hit... I was a lot better than I had been [...], because I'd been sort of virtually in lockdown for a year before, really, I had been getting better, but I, I hadn't done a great deal in '19 and then, when we eventually went into lockdown, I enjoyed it. [laughs] Because my life had shrunk anyway, so it didn't make much difference to me and the weather was fabulous and I could, I could go out for an hour. I didn't have to do more." [R2_F5].

Other participants specifically highlighted how they had benefitted from digital technologies during the pandemic, with one noting how isolation a friend of hers had felt because she had no internet access: *"Because you could get so much on your iPad, you could get films and books or anything you wanted. I didn't ever feel, although I was obviously isolating because of my age, I didn't feel as cut off. Now somebody I know, we got a message via another group saying she was really feeling, feeling isolated. She hadn't got anything. And so people were being asked would they phone her, because she was really missing out. Whereas I didn't, I didn't really feel as cut off and I think it was because of having access."* [R1_F2]. For this participant, *"technology was great. Because certainly in the earlier days, you felt you were still part of the community..."* Communication apps were also

valued by R1_F3, who used them to keep in touch with family: *"I did Facetime the family a lot... [...] and then I can do the same with using the video thing on WhatsApp and Facetime with my niece in Australia and my cousin in Australia, so I didn't feel particularly isolated really."* Another participant, whose general technology usage was low, acknowledged the role that technology had played in helping her through the pandemic: *"I follow a farm, a man, Cannon Hall Farm. So I, I'm... That got me through Covid. He, that man, got me through."* [R1_F4]. However, for many, technology could not substitute interacting with people, with one explaining that while her phone was her *"companion"* when living on her own, moving in with her family during the pandemic was *"heaven on earth."* [R2_F2]. Similarly, a participant who thought Zoom meetings could not replace human interaction, explained how he *"never really believed in Zoom meetings. I always found I wanted to talk face to face to people."* [R1_M3]. This participant, instead of meeting representatives from some contractors he was working with on Zoom during lockdown, was glad they managed to meet *"in isolated circumstances."* (ibid.). Technology also did little to alleviate the anxieties of the participant whose husband had to move out for three months to look after his ill father. Describing her fear at being left alone during that time, she explained that although they rang *"each other every day [...] I was at home on my own and [...] I thought, oh my goodness, somebody's going to find me dead one day."* [R2_F8].

4.3 Confidence in Using Technology

Many of the people we interviewed needed help with technology during the rapid digitalisation that took place following the onset of the pandemic. How fine the line here could be between them gaining or losing confidence

was made apparent by the participant who told us how, when *"the lockdown started, that's when they decided to have these Zoom meetings. So I went on with one of the girls who were quite conversant with computers, she went on there with me, and it was great and I could speak to all these people abroad [...] But then I went on myself [...] Pressed the wrong button. Went silent. [...] And ... they're all there trying to help me. [...] I said I'm not doing it again. It's too embarrassing. [...] So I haven't done it ever since."*

[R1_M2]. Also talking about using Zoom, another participant said that she could not have achieved this on her own: *"When we were in, in lockdown, erm, and I, I attend [name of church]... we were asked to do various services online and via Zoom and, erm, I said, "No, I can't do that. I, I, I just can't do that. That's beyond me." However, a much younger colleague came and showed me how to do it. [...] I could never have done it following instruction [...]"* [R2_F6].

Sometimes, negative past experiences with technology played a role in undermining the confidence in learning digital technology, such as for the participant who had to rely on social services and her local doctor's surgery for food parcels when she caught COVID: *"With, with my husband being ill... [...] I couldn't go out. So I got sick... They'd come [...] with food for me because I wasn't allowed to go out... [...] It kept me going."* [R2_F10]. Another participant explained that her daughter helped her register for online banking and use it when she moved in with her during the pandemic [R2_F2].

For many, however, social distancing during the pandemic and the impossibility of in-person support had negative impacts on their use of digital technology. One participant observed that the lack of support and the effects of being on their own made people "draw into themselves," which "destroyed their confidence in using technologies." [R1_F5]. Another, who

was involved in running online courses via Zoom during the pandemic, noted that *"Some [people] didn't join on Zoom"* and how the groups *"just lost touch with them"*. He felt that their non-attendance was probably more likely to do with them not knowing what to do with a device rather than not having a device: *"I'm not sure about access, in the sense of having a, a device. Knowing how, what to do with it, I think is the [reason]."* [R2_M3]. As shown in the literature review above, a lack of digital skills is a key contributing factor in digital exclusion.

Several participants, particularly those aged 80 and over who were under-confident or did not use digital technologies pre-pandemic, did not increase their use during the pandemic. For example, R2_F1, who had a smartphone, never used it: *"No, I just didn't then. I only had this this phone. I've never bothered with anything else at all. No. Bit lazy perhaps."* Some relied on their sons and/or daughters to complete technological tasks on their behalf, such as online shopping and ordering prescriptions: *"[...] my daughters are quite up with all this technology. So if I've got any appointments, say I want something urgent, they will do it for me, you know?"* [R2_F3].

Confidence was boosted for those who frequently used digital technology, , for example, R2_F6: *"I do use Zoom, and I know how to do it. [...] [W]e ... started using it for the U3A Spanish class that I go to, and I was also running a German group with U3A, and we started doing that on Zoom. That has now gone back to face-to-face contact. Yeah, but I still use Zoom for all kinds of things..."* Another participant, due to his now frequent use of Zoom, told us how he *"stopped being scared of it."* [R2_M3].

A number of participants, many of whom had not learnt how to use digital technology, relied on family to liaise with surgeries, order

prescriptions and book appointments on their behalf regarding mHealth. For example, one respondent explained that her daughters were “*quite up with all this technology. So if I've got any appointments, say I want something urgent, they will do it for me, you know?*” [R2_F4], while another observed: “*Actually our [name of daughter] used to do all that. She got them to phone her about everything so she knew I didn't, I didn't have to.*” [R2_F1]. Of the few respondents who had had telephone consultations, many not happy about the difficulties they experienced in seeing doctors in person, which they would have preferred.

CONCLUSION

With digital technology permeating so many areas of modern-day living, it can be difficult to separate someone’s day-to-day experiences of navigating life, particularly during crisis situations such as pandemics, without acknowledging how technology usage, or lack of usage, has impacted that life.

Some common themes have, nevertheless, emerged from our purposive literature review and the empirical research we conducted. First, digitalisation undoubtedly accelerated rapidly in most countries as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, changing practices in many areas of life, most notably shopping, banking, working, socialising, and healthcare. Secondly, it appears that digital technology usage in many spheres of life has, as a result, increased. However, this has not happened evenly, neither in a geographical nor a demographic sense. While some countries, like Sweden

and Estonia, for example, already had advanced digitalisation as the pandemic broke out and their populations were well acquainted with many forms of digital technology, in other countries such as Saudi Arabia, this was not the case. Thirdly, digital exclusion and the digital divide were experienced to different degrees across and within different countries, regions, and population groups. While our report shows that some older adults – the focus of this report – were already well acquainted with different forms of digital technology (smartphones, laptops, internet) when COVID-19 broke out, others felt forced by the pandemic and subsequent lockdowns to use them more or learn how to use them, often without in-person support. This impacted on how digital technology was experienced and is likely to impact on continued or increased usage. Fourth, technical support – either provided by family, friends, or the State is essential for helping older adults cope with digitalisation (for specific initiatives mentioned in this report, see the summary following the Conclusion). Fifth, apart from providing many benefits, there are many concerns about the impacts that digital technology has on human communication and interaction. Many of the participants in our study, for example, were deeply concerned about how digital technology impacted personal relationships and many mentioned that technology should not replace people. They were also concerned about job losses, impacts on local economies, and impacts on daily practices. This highlights that there are many areas of digitalisation where further research is urgently required, and where public engagement relating to the digital futures we are in the process of creating is needed. We hope that this report will contribute to the latter.

APPENDIX 1 - STRATEGIES ADOPTED TO SUPPORT OLDER ADULTS

- In the **United Kingdom**, a **Digital Lifeline Fund** was launched by the UK Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS) in March 2021 as a response to COVID-19's impact on digitally excluded populations, especially adults with learning disabilities and older adults. Through this fund (£2.5 million) tablets, internet connections, and digital skills support were provided through partnerships with charities to deliver tailored support. Success factors here were that a holistic approach was taken that encompassed tech and data provision plus training with emphasis on inclusion and accessibility. Another notable strategy for overcoming digital exclusion adopted by the **UK** in 2022 was the **Digital Champion Programme**. As part of this programme, Digital Champion volunteers (often older adults themselves) are recruited and trained to help older people improve their digital skills. The program also loans technology to those lacking access to it³. We discuss this further in the empirical section.
- Another European was the **Digital Solidarity Initiative (Solidarietà Digitale)** of **Italy**, which was launched in the early days of Italy's nationwide lockdown (March 2020) to offer free digital services (e.g., ebooks, video conferencing, training) to the general public. Here, too, the focus was on inclusion. This was a public-private initiative where companies offered free services to help seniors and others stay informed, entertained, and connected during lockdown. The initiative was taken swiftly, and its success largely depended on the partnerships formed with tech firms and media outlets.

³ <https://www.ageuk.org.uk/our-impact/programmes/digital-skills/digital-champions/>

- Although already launched in 2018, prior to the pandemic, the **Connected Canadians** initiative **Tech Mentorship for Seniors** was scaled significantly in 2020 to support older adults during lockdowns. Volunteer-driven and not-for-profit, free digital literacy training was made available to older adults that focused on empowering rather than just teaching them. This took place in form of one-on-one virtual sessions and through workshops. Among the success factors here were that volunteers were tech professionals, and that support was personalized and characterised by ongoing mentorship.
- To overcome the digital skills gap between young and old, facilitate the social well-being of older adults during lockdown, and accelerate digital adoption generally, the **Singaporean** government (Infocomm Media Development Authority (IMDA)) launched the **Seniors Go Digital programme** in June 2020. The programme included the provision of virtual event platforms that offered web-based services, gaming programs, virtual reality platforms, mobile applications, and social networks. To ensure that older Singaporeans had access to these opportunities, the Government subsidised mobile data plans for mobile phones and other gadgets and made funds available for the training of **Digital Ambassadors** who would teach older adults basic digital skills. They provided one-on-one coaching at community centres, libraries, and even homes. Topics taught included using smartphones, video calls, QR code scanning (for contact tracing), and digital payments. Over 100,000 seniors trained within the first year. Success factors here were: strong government backing, collaboration with grassroots organizations, and free devices provided for low-income seniors.

- The **Australian** National Digital Literacy Program for older Australians, **“Be Connected,”** was launched in 2017 and expanded in 2020. It received extra funding from the Government, which enabled it to expand its outreach activities to support seniors impacted by lockdowns and service closures. The initiative was run by the Australian government in partnership with the Good Things Foundation. As part of it, online learning resources, grants to community partners, and a national helpline was made available. Its success was helped by Australia’s long-standing infrastructure, which was adapted for COVID-19, and the scalable, blended delivery model (online and local centres) adopted.
- In **South Korea**, an **AI Speaker and Smart Devices for Seniors** Initiative, the **Smart Care Home Program**, was launched in late 2020. Here, AI-powered speakers were provided to isolated older adults living alone. The speakers offered reminders, emergency contact options, and companionship as well as monitoring signs of cognitive decline through voice interaction. Here, it is noteworthy that AI was specifically used for mental health support, and that the initiative was based on Government-private sector collaborations (e.g., with SK Telecom).

APPENDIX 2 – RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

This report has highlighted some of the consequences that the rapid digitalisation spurred by the COVID-19 pandemic has had on older adults throughout the world, and how it has impacted them in both positive and negative ways. The pros and cons of digitalisation are not easy to grasp, not least because we are dealing with many moving targets. While digitalisation continues apace, digital technologies themselves are changing fast. Similarly, “ageing” – as a biological process – reminds us that time does not stand still and that generational changes unfold as we watch, while “age” and “ageing” – as social constructs – present us with varying socio-cultural understanding and definition that need to be taken into account. Finally, people’s attitudes and experiences of technology and digital technology greatly vary, as do their personal circumstances. This makes the study of digital exclusion and digital equity for older adults a highly complex, challenging topic.

The studies discussed in this report nevertheless provide some useful pointers as to where further research is required, including on:

- What factors influence digital exclusion/inclusion – e.g. geographical, socio-economic, demographic, cultural, educational, psychological, but also, infrastructure, policy, government initiatives, and more. How do these factors matter, individually and combined?
- What works regarding helping older adults become confident digital technology users? E.g. Community, family, communities of practice, digital champions, TV educational programmes, online and in-person help, and more. What has the pandemic taught us here?
- How does digital technology usage affect mental health and well-being? What should we do to avoid and address negative impacts?
- Why do many people, in spite of being able to connect more easily with family and friends, appear to feel lonelier as a result of digital technology usage? What lessons does this teach us?
- What measures can we put in place to ensure that digital technology will not increasingly replace human contact and undermine non-digital knowledges and skills?

- How can the increasing gap between digitally included and digitally excluded people be closed? What social justice issues need to be urgently addressed here?
- What could the future consequences of digitalisation be for humans, other lifeforms, and the environment?
- Who decides where digitalisation is and should be taking us?

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MEET THE TEAM

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To meet all team members and learn more about our interests and expertise, please visit our project website, where you will find more information about us here:

<https://wp.lancs.ac.uk/digi-age/project-team/>

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